

Oligomeric structure and molecular chaperone function of eye lens protein α -crystallin – A Review

Sudipa Saha

Department of Biotechnology, St. Xavier's College, Kolkata-700 016, India

E-mail : sahasudipa74@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : α -Crystallin, the major eye lens protein, exists as a large oligomer of two subunits, α A- and α B-crystallin. α -Crystallin exists in solution as a polydisperse high molecular mass aggregate with a molecular weight distribution ranging from 300,000 to over 1 million. Crystallization attempts of both the natural and recombinant α -crystallin of vertebrate were not fruitful so far because of the polydispersed nature of the protein oligomer. It is seen that despite the enormous number of studies on the structure of α -crystallin, the oligomeric structure of α -crystallin is still the subject of much debate and speculation. It is generally believed that large oligomeric structure of α -crystallin or other sHSPs is prerequisite for their chaperone-like function. Although most chaperones are oligomers, whether oligomerization is absolutely required for protein stability or for chaperone function is not yet established.

Keywords : α -Crystallin, molecular chaperone, oligomeric size, thermal aggregation, light scattering, hydrophobicity, subunit exchange, binding sites.

1. Introduction

The main constituents of the mammalian eye lens fiber cells are crystallin proteins namely α -, β - and γ -crystallin¹. Among all the crystallins, α -crystallin is the major protein and responsible for maintaining the transparency and refractive properties of the eye lens^{2,3}. The term "crystallin" means the structural proteins. In birds and reptiles, there is another major lens protein called δ -crystallin^{4,5}. There are many other crystallins which are known as taxon-specific crystallins⁶⁻⁸. There are two α -crystallin genes, giving rise to α A- and α B-crystallin. In the mammalian lens, the molar ratio of α A to α B is about 3 : 1¹. In humans, α A-crystallin has 173 and α B-crystallin has 175 amino acid residues. There is about 57% amino acid sequence identity between α A- and α B-crystallin⁶.

Although it was believed for many years that α -crystallin was strictly lens-specific protein, both α A- and α B-crystallin have now been found in many non-lenticular tissues⁹⁻¹². α A- and α B-Crystallin have been linked to various neurological diseases such as Alexander's disease⁹, Creutzfeldt-Jacob disease^{13,14}, Alzheimer's disease¹⁰, Parkinson's disease¹³, Lewy body disease¹⁵. Fur-

thermore, α -crystallin is a key member of the small heat shock protein (sHSPs) family and its structural and functional similarities are conserved from bacteria to humans¹⁶⁻²⁰. α B-Crystallin is known to be inducible by various stress conditions such as heat shock or oxidative stress^{17,21} and α A- and α B-crystallin are able to confer cellular thermoresistance^{22,23}. Finally, α -crystallin like other sHSPs has been found to act as molecular chaperone *in vitro* by preventing the aggregation of other proteins under thermal stress or other stress conditions^{3,24-29}. Although the chaperone activity of α -crystallin *in vivo* is well known²⁶, the molecular mechanisms of the chaperone function of α -crystallin still remains unknown.

α -Crystallin is present in the lens in a very concentrated form. In the center of a human lens the concentration of protein is about 450 mg/ml³⁰. The crystallins generally form 90% or more of the total protein mass in which the contribution of α -crystallin is only 45%. The other crystallins such as β -crystallin contributes 20% and γ -crystallin 35%. A unique property of the lens is the lack of protein turnover in the differentiated fiber cells. The lens does not have any mechanism to dispose the damaged proteins, whereas the other tissues in the body,

most of the enzymes in the liver, for example, turnover in minutes, hours or days. The lens fiber cells and their proteins must survive for life. The mechanism by which the protein mass remains transparent over such a long period has thus become a subject of intense investigations.

2. Oligomeric structure of α -crystallin

Crystallization attempts of both the natural and recombinant α -crystallin of vertebrate were not fruitful so far because of the polydispersed nature of the protein oligomer. The detailed 3D structure of the subunit and also the topology of the oligomeric assembly are not known. Cryo-electron microscopic data indicates that recombinant human α B-crystallin assembly consists mainly of protein shells of ~ 19 nm diameter with a diameter of ~ 8 nm in central cavity³¹. The oligomeric structure of α -crystallin has been the subject of much debate and speculation. α -Crystallin exists in solution as a polydisperse high molecular mass aggregate with a molecular weight distribution ranging from 300,000 to over 1 million. The models, proposed to describe the oligomeric structure of α -crystallin, can be divided into three main groups: the three-layer models, the micelle-like models and the models of tetrameric building blocks^{2,32}. Other models such as rhombododecahedral structure³³, a two-layer structure composed of annuli of peptides³⁴ have also been proposed. A "pitted-flexiball" model suggested that tetrameric subunit building blocks were combined in an open micelle-like arrangement³⁵. Due to the polydisperse nature, crystal structure of α -crystallin is not available. Recently, a few sHSPs have been studied by cryo-electron microscopy³⁶. By this technique, α B-crystallin was found to have a variable oligomeric structure with a central cavity³¹. Even though cryo-electron microscopy of HSP 16.5 yielded regular and symmetric assemblies, no clear symmetry was obtained for α -crystallin or HSP 27. On the other hand, it was observed that there were variable assemblies of α -crystallin. Electron microscopic data revealed that α -crystallin consists of globular particles of diameter 14–18 nm³⁷ and can have a torus-like structure³⁸.

3. Molecular chaperone function of α -crystallin

Investigations on α -crystallin structure and function

took a new turn when Horwitz (1992) reported for the first time that α -crystallin has molecular chaperone-like properties. He showed that α -crystallin was able to prevent the heat-induced aggregation of a number of proteins including β - and γ -crystallin. He proposed that this is a physiological function of this protein, which plays vital role in maintaining the transparency of the lens *in vivo*. Later, it was shown that α -crystallin not only prevented thermal aggregation of proteins, but also prevented disulphide bond cleavage and UV-light exposure-induced aggregation of proteins as well. The chaperone function of α -crystallin has been the subject of interest and functional models have been suggested^{18,34,39,40}.

3.1. Substrate specificity :

Damage of proteins may occur in the lens due to various reasons such as oxidative stress, ultraviolet radiation or any other kind of stress. When proteins are damaged, they may aggregate forming large insoluble particles. This is detrimental to the transparency of the lens. α -Crystallin, the major protein of the eye lens, captures these denaturing proteins, keeping them in soluble form. The disulphide bond of insulin gets cleaved in presence of DTT and insulin B-chain gets aggregated. In presence of α -crystallin, this aggregation is prevented indicating that insulin B-chain is bound by α -crystallin. The substrate is bound by α -crystallin only in stress condition. α -Crystallin does not bind any substrate in its native state, it binds substrate when it tends to aggregate. The heat induced aggregation of many enzymes such as α -glucosidase, enolase, alcohol dehydrogenase, carbonic anhydrase, citrate synthase, lactate dehydrogenase, aldolase, phosphoglucose isomerase is prevented in presence of α -crystallin. These substrates may have implications for *in vitro* studies, but substrates of *in vivo* relevance to eye lens α -crystallin are β -crystallin, γ -crystallin, aldose reductase etc. whose aggregation under various conditions are also prevented by α -crystallin^{26,28,29,41–45}.

The hydrophobic pockets present in the surface of α -crystallin have been suggested to be prerequisite for the chaperone function of α -crystallin²⁸. The chaperone activity of α -crystallin is largely studied using thermal aggregation of protein as assay system. The aggregation experiments were performed with different substrates using the temperature range between approximately 45 and

65 °C^{26,29,46}. There must be some conformational change of α -crystallin at elevated temperature along with denaturation of substrate. α -Crystallin undergoes a conformational transition between approximately 38 and 50 °C (Fig. 1). Bis-ANS binding study showed that this transition was due to an increase in exposure of hydrophobic surfaces²⁴. α -Crystallin preincubated at higher temperature is more efficient in preventing insulin aggregation revealing positive correlation between surface hydrophobicity and chaperone activity of α -crystallin (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of fluorescence emission intensity (490 nm) of bis-ANS (13 μ M) in presence of α -crystallin (0.06 mg/ml) in 50 mM phosphate buffer, pH 7.2. (■) First heating cycle; (×) first cooling cycle; (□) second heating cycle (This research was originally published in *FEBS Lett.*, 1995, **369**, 321. © Elsevier. Ref. 24).

It was seen that in presence of 3 M urea, quaternary structure of α -crystallin was perturbed and its chaperone activity against photoaggregation of γ -crystallin was enhanced²⁸. Thus not only the thermotropic changes, quaternary structural perturbation of α -crystallin by nonthermal mode also results in enhancement of chaperone activity. Raman *et al.* also studied the refolding properties of α -, β - and γ -crystallins by the method of rapid refolding which was achieved by diluting the sample with refolding buffer⁴⁷. It was shown that when α -crystallin was refolded together with β - or γ -crystallin, the recov-

Fig. 2. DTT induced aggregation of insulin B chain at 22 °C in absence and presence of α -crystallin (0.125 mg/ml) preincubated at different temperature. (A) No α -crystallin; (B) α -crystallin preincubated at 22 °C; (C) α -crystallin preincubated at 50 °C; (D) α -crystallin preincubated at 60 °C (This research was originally published in *FEBS Lett.*, 1995, **369**, 321. © Elsevier. Ref. 24).

ery of β - or γ -crystallin in the solution increased significantly whereas the native α -crystallin was less effective in preventing the aggregation of β - or γ -crystallin. It was suggested that an intermediate state of α -crystallin was formed in its refolding pathway and this state was more effective in chaperone activity compared with the native state.

Besides aggregation prevention, α -crystallin has also been found to reactivate enzymes, refolding from unfolded conditions⁴⁸⁻⁵². Reactivations occur under extremely dilute condition of the enzyme, where its self aggregation is minimized. Reactivations occur over a period of about one hour with maximum activity recovered being in the range 10-30% in most cases⁴⁹⁻⁵². Although ATP has been reported to yield marginally higher activity^{48,49,51,52}, the requirement of ATP hydrolysis has been questioned^{48,50}. The association in presence of ATP was also demonstrated by gel filtration chromatography using γ -crystallin covalently labeled with a highly fluorescence probe FITC and monitoring FITC fluorescence (Fig. 3). While free γ -crystallin eluted at 22 min, incuba-

Fig. 3. ATP induced association between substrate and α A-crystallin at different temperatures, determined by gel filtration method. FITC tagged γ -crystallin (0.25 mg/ml) and human α A-crystallin (0.25 mg/ml) in 50 mM phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 were incubated with or without 3 mM ATP or ATP- γ -S for 1 h at various temperature. The mixture was brought to 25 °C and then 20 μ L of it was injected to the column pre-equilibrated with the same buffer with or without 3 mM ATP or ATP- γ -S. Trace 1, no ATP, 25 °C; trace 2, +ATP, 25 °C; trace 3, no ATP, 37 °C; trace 4, +ATP, 37 °C; trace 5, +ATP- γ -S, 37 °C (This research was originally published in *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2004, **279**, 42648. © the American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology. Ref. 48).

tion of γ -crystallin with α -crystallin in presence of ATP above 37 °C reduced the peak at 22 min and a new peak at 10 min appeared confirming the high molecular mass associated complex of γ -crystallin with α -crystallin. Thus contrary to the common belief that ATP causes dissociation of the chaperone-substrate complex it actually induces complex formation at the physiological temperature. The measurement of surface hydrophobicity of α -crystallin bis-ANS showed that ATP opened up additional hydrophobic sites on α -crystallin surface, but not on the substrate protein γ -crystallin or carbonic anhydrase (Fig. 4). It has been found that unlike GroEL-substrate complex, ATP did not dissociate α -crystallin-substrate complex, but instead it enhanced the association and improved chaperone activity⁴⁸. Whether the refolding activity of α -crystallin has any physiological role in eye lens is not yet known.

Fig. 4. Bis-ANS binding to various α -crystallin and its substrate γ -crystallin in the presence (open symbols) and absence (closed symbols) of 3 mM ATP. (A) α A-Crystallin, 37 °C; (B) α B-Crystallin, 37 °C and (C) γ -crystallin, 37 °C. Protein concentration in all samples was 50 μ g/ml in 50 μ M phosphate buffer, pH 7.2. Excitation wavelength of 390 nm and emission wavelength of 490 nm were used (This research was originally published in *J. Biol. Chem.*, 2004, **279**, 42648. © the American Society for Biochemistry and Molecular Biology. Ref. 48).

3.2. Substrate-binding sites :

One of the important aspects of α -crystallin chaperone function is the characterization of the substrate binding sites. It is generally believed that substrate is bound to the hydrophobic regions of chaperone α -crystallin. In case of GroEL, it has been suggested that surface hydrophobicity is a necessary characteristic of both the substrate and chaperone for favourable interaction⁵³⁻⁵⁷. A direct correlation between the surface hydrophobicity and chaperone activity of α -crystallin has been reported by many workers^{24,47,58,59}. The mechanistic details of such a correlation is yet to be fully understood, as some results showed that higher chaperone activity was not accompanied by concomitant increase in hydrophobicity⁶⁰⁻⁶². Further studies are needed to understand the relationship between such parameters.

The binding of bis-ANS reduced the chaperone activity of α -crystallin^{53,63-70}. These studies as well as others

indicate that regions interacting with bis-ANS are identical with sites that bind substrate proteins^{71,72}. These data collectively indicate that fluorescent probes and substrate proteins have common binding sites. It was seen that in rat α B-crystallin bis-ANS was bound to the N-terminal domain⁷³. Incorporation of fluorescent dyes into the N-terminal region was also observed in bovine α A-crystallin⁶⁵. These results show that N-terminal region of α -crystallin contributes to substrate binding.

The substrate binding sites have been also reported to be located in the α -crystallin domain^{69,72}. Cross-linking studies with denatured alcohol dehydrogenase (ADH) or mellitin, a 2.8 kDa hydrophobic polypeptide, to bovine α A- and α B-crystallin demonstrated similar sites to those defined by bis-ANS labelling^{71,72}. Two binding sites were located between residues 57 and 69 and residues 93 and 107 in case of ADH, whereas the single binding was observed between residues 75 and 82 for mellitin. A synthetic 19-residue peptide from the α -crystallin domain (residues 70–88) of human α A-crystallin prevented thermal aggregation of ADH⁷². This peptide was also shown to bind bis-ANS. Thus we can say that multiple regions are involved in substrate binding. Whether different substrates are sequestered at different binding sites is still an open question.

The thiol-containing region of α A-crystallin (at positions 131 and 141) is known to play a role in chaperone activity. This region is the contact region of α -crystallin domain and the flexible C-terminal tail, which contains a good number of charged residues. The role of the charged residues in substrate binding has not been explored in detail. Thiol residues may serve as markers to probe possible substrate binding sites or substrate induced changes in this region⁷⁴.

4. Oligomeric structure vs molecular chaperone function of α -crystallin

A very common feature to most sHSPs including α -crystallin is their ability to form large micelle-like oligomeric complexes^{20,75–78}. In lens, α A- and α B-crystallin exist as polydisperse heteroaggregates of average molecular mass of ~ 800 kDa^{2,26}. Homoaggregates of recombinant α A- and α B-crystallin have molecular mass ~ 650 kDa⁷⁹. HSP 16.5, whose crystal structure is known, formed a 24-subunit assembly of approximately 400 kDa⁸⁰.

Electron micrographic images of HSP 26 and HSP 27 showed spherical multisubunit assembly^{81,82}. Many other classical molecular chaperones such as GroEL, TriC are also known to have large oligomeric structure^{79,83}. It is generally believed that large oligomeric structure of α -crystallin or other sHSPs is prerequisite for their chaperone-like function^{18,20}. This notion exists because studies showed that both naturally occurring α -crystallin, defective in oligomerization, and mutated variants that did not form oligomers were poor chaperones^{84–87}. Examples are also abundant for other sHSPs showing poor chaperone activity with reduction in oligomeric size^{88–90}. It has been reported that genetically engineered α B-crystallin containing only the α -crystallin domain formed a dimer, but showed considerable chaperone activity⁹¹. Due to point mutation R120G of α B-crystallin, oligomeric size was doubled, but its chaperone activity was lost⁹². Although some point mutations in α B-crystallin formed enlarged assemblies, but chaperone activity remained unchanged^{35,92}. After deletion of last 17-residues from the

Fig. 5. SDS-PAGE of α A-crystallin (panel A) and α B-crystallin (panel B) digested with trypsin for various time. Panel A : lane 1, 0 min; lane 2, 15 min; lane 3, 30 min; lane 4, 45 min; lane 5, 1 h; lane 6, 1.5 h; lane 7, 2 h; lane 8, 3 h. Panel B : lane 1, 0 min; lane 2, 15 min; lane 3, 30 min; lane 4, 1 h; lane 5, 2 h; lane 6, 3 h; lane 7, 5 h; lane 8, 8 h (This research was originally published in *Proteins*, 2004, 57, 610. © Wiley Periodicals, Inc. Ref. 97).

C-terminal tail of α A-crystallin, its oligomeric size was increased, but chaperone activity drastically reduced. A small heat shock protein was identified from human called HSP 22, which existed as monomer, but showed chaperone-like activity⁹³. It has also been proposed that dimer or tetramer of subunits of α -crystallin was active as chaperone⁹⁴. Hsp18.5 from *Arabidopsis thaliana* was dimeric and exhibited robust chaperone activity⁹⁵. A P39R mutation at the N-terminal domain of human α B-crystallin regulated its oligomeric state and chaperone-like activity⁹⁶. Tryptic digested fragments of both α A- and α B-crystallin much smaller than the original subunits retained

considerable chaperone activity⁹⁷. α A- and α B-crystallin were digested under controlled condition for various length of time. The bands of α -crystallin appeared ranging from 12 to 20 kDa on SDS PAGE (Fig. 5). The oligomeric size of the resultant oligomers were compared by three different methods namely gel filtration chromatography, membrane filtration method and light scattering technique. Gel filtration experiment showed only two types of oligomer one around 500 kDa and others are below 20 kDa (Fig. 6A). The oligomers were divided into two categories above and below 100 kDa through membrane filtration method (Fig. 6B). 90° light scattering measurement

Fig. 6. Determination of oligomeric size of recombinant α A- and α B-crystallin with the progress of tryptic digestion by various methods. (A) Gel filtration profile of digested α A-crystallin as a function of digestion time. Trace 1, 30 min; trace 2, 1 h; trace 3, 2 h; trace 4, 6 h. (B) Centrifugal filtration through 100 kDa membrane. Percentage of α A- and α B-crystallin passing through the membrane was shown as a function of digestion time. (C) 90° Light scattering as measured in a fluorimeter of α A- and α B-crystallin solution as a function of the digestion time. Scattering was measured at 37 °C using 400 nm as excitation and emission wavelength, using 0.2 mg/ml protein solution plus trypsin; ratio between α -crystallin and trypsin being 100 : 1 (by wt.) in 50 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 (This research was originally published in *Proteins*, 2004, 57, 610. © Wiley Periodicals, Inc. Ref. 97).

in a fluorimeter showed a general decrease in oligomeric size with increase in digestion time (Fig. 6C).

The oxidation lead to disintegration of the oligomeric structure of α A- and α B-crystallins and it appeared that the formation of the low molecular weight proteins was the primary cause of the chaperone activity loss due to oxidation⁹⁸. Small heat shock protein activity was regulated by variable oligomeric substructure⁹⁹. The deletion from the N-terminal beyond the first 20 residues drastically reduced the oligomeric association of α A-crystallin and its complete removal resulted in a tetramer. Chaperone activity of α A-crystallin decreased with increasing length of deletion and little activity was observed for the tetramer¹⁰⁰. By unfolding and refolding of bovine α -crystallin in urea, it was shown that although refolded form was smaller in oligomeric size but showed higher chaperone activity¹⁰¹. It was shown that the secondary structure as monitored by the ellipticity of α -crystallin during unfolding and refolding was fully reversible (Fig. 7). But the tertiary and quaternary structures of the refolded α -

Fig. 7. Unfolding and refolding profiles of α -crystallin observed by circular dichroic measurement. Ellipticity (θ) at 222 nm for unfolding (solid square) and refolding (open circle) of α -crystallin was plotted against urea concentration. Concentration of α -crystallin was 0.5 mg/mL in 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.2 (This research was originally published in *Proteins J.*, 2007, **26**, 315. © Springer, Netherlands. Ref. 108).

Fig. 8. Binding of bis-ANS by native and urea-refolded α -crystallin. Fluorescence emission intensity at 490 nm was measured as a function of bis-ANS concentration taking excitation wavelength 390 nm for native (solid circle) and urea-refolded (solid square) α -crystallin. α -Crystallin concentration was 0.1 mg/ml (This research was originally published in *Proteins J.*, 2007, **26**, 315. © Springer, Netherlands. Ref. 108).

crystallin were slightly different from that of the native state. The bis-ANS titration data demonstrated that the refolded form has higher exposed hydrophobicity than the native α -crystallin revealing that refolded form had lower oligomeric size and higher chaperone activity (Fig. 8).

Concluding Remarks

From the above discussion, it is seen that despite the enormous number of studies on the structure of α -crystallin, the tertiary and quaternary structure of α -crystallin is still the subject of much debate and speculation. Although most chaperones are oligomers, whether oligomerization is absolutely required for protein stability or for chaperone function is not established. All these data indicate that there is a great deal of controversy regarding the relationship between the oligomeric size and chaperone activity of α -crystallin.

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